

How do teacher educators affect their students?

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Steiner teacher educators work with at least two kinds of knowledge: outer knowledge – what to do, curriculum, techniques of teaching, resources and so on – and inner knowledge. It is inner knowledge which I would like to explore a little further today, especially how it relates to the relationship between the teacher educator and student teacher (perhaps more simply expressed as adult to adult).

Many educators and theorists have recognised the profound effect teachers have on those they teach. Steiner is one voice in a much wider conversation. We hear it in Parker Palmer’s observation that *we teach who we are*. We can also hear it in Vygotsky’s understanding that learning takes place within a relational space, shaped by the presence of someone more knowledgeable or experienced than the student. Across different traditions, the same insight is emphasised: the being of the educator is a central part of the educational process, the educational environment.

I find Steiner’s contribution to this conversation transformational because he places the inner being of the teacher at the centre of pedagogical activity. As Steiner says in the second lecture of the *Curative Course* (GA 317), “You have no idea how unimportant what the teacher says or does not say is on the surface, and how important the teacher’s own being is.” Palmer and Vygotsky are widely taught in teacher education courses, yet Steiner’s pedagogical law offers a deeper insight and covers the whole of human life from before birth onwards.

In the *Curative Course*, Steiner talks about the ‘proper’ development of the different bodies/members of the human being. He describes a chain of influence in which each developing member of the young person is formed by the next higher member of the adult (parents, teachers). He draws this table:

Student	Adult
Physical	Etheric
Etheric	Astral
Astral	Ego
Ego	Spirit Self

And says,

Any one member of the human being is influenced by the next higher member (from whatever quarter it approaches) and only under such influence can that member develop satisfactorily. Thus, whatever is to be effective for the development of the physical body must be living in the etheric body – in an etheric body.

‘Only’ is a strong word in this context. Carrying this through, we have the developing ego of the student ‘only’ able to achieve a healthy development when influenced by the Spirit Self of those around them.

If the developing ego of high school students are shaped by the Spirit Self of the adult, then we as adults must understand what Spirit Self is. In the first chapter of *Theosophy*, Steiner describes the Spirit Self as the member of the human being which we, as a human race, are working towards developing and which will only be completed in the Jupiter stage of Earth’s evolution, far in the future. However, we are all working on it now. Steiner characterises the Spirit Self as the transformed astral body – that is, the astral body reshaped through the conscious activity of the I.

In this way, it is not a ‘next stage’ or something ‘new’, it is a transformation of what is already there. When the I takes hold of its own reactions, impulses, emotions and inner life, and reshapes them through truth and moral insight, the astral body transforms into Spirit Self. In the untransformed astral body, we are borne along by likes, dislikes, emotions and shifting impressions. In the Spirit Self, these same soul forces become ordered and clarified by what is true, what is good, and by spiritual intuition. The soul becomes an organ of understanding rather than an assemblage of instincts and reactions.

A key to the development of the Spirit Self is that truth becomes an inner organising force. Instead of truth being something we think about, talk about or have ideas about, it begins to shape who we are. The I absorbs truth and lets it permeate the astral body, gradually transforming it from within. Spirit Self develops gradually through everyday acts of clear thinking, of self-mastery, through moral imagination and genuine inner work. Whenever the I brings clarity where there was confusion or fuzzy-headedness, or steadiness where there was impulse, the Spirit Self is being developed.

This is challenging, as we are all still in the process of developing the Spirit Self, and none of us has it developed fully. Nonetheless, this is the picture which Steiner gives, while acknowledging its awkwardness. It is not only an ideal; Steiner says that even the Spirit Self of what he calls the ‘worst possible teacher’ will influence the development of the ego of the young person, in this case, negatively.

He comments about the next stage, “I could continue and go beyond the Spirit Self, but there we should be entering the field of esoteric instruction.” If Steiner gave this table for students up to the age of 21, when ego development is complete, what applies to

those who work with adults? For me, this brings up many questions about teacher education.

As we work with inner and outer knowledge, material and spiritual, we operate on two different levels. On one hand we have the usual aspects of professional competence, mastering ideas and concepts, understanding curricula, and so on, while on the other there is a fundamental question about what I might call the *level of being* we bring to our work, and of what we aim to cultivate through it.

When we teach about child development, pedagogical approaches, consider curriculum content, work with resources or artistic practice, we might easily fall into thinking that this is the primary task. But there is an important question to consider – by concentrating on this (and it needs concentrating on) what are we not considering? Once the learner has reached adulthood, how much of the pedagogical law still holds?

This raises further questions for us as teacher educators: What else are we responsible for cultivating in our students? How do we support their inner development, not only through what we do but through who we are? Are we unintentionally hindering this development by focusing too narrowly on teaching practices, unwittingly putting a ceiling on their development? Or are we consciously creating conditions in which their inner life can grow?

For me, these questions open the door to considering the inner development of the teacher educator, not as an abstract ideal but as a practical condition for real pedagogical activity as well as an undoubted responsibility. Steiner's pedagogical law points us toward this: the teacher's inner life is not an "addition" to their teaching; it determines what can arise in the other person. The significance of the inner nature of the teacher is clear from the first lecture of the *First Teachers' Course*. If so, then mapping the inner development of the *teacher educator* – the one who supports the becoming of teachers – becomes crucial, even though it is largely uncharted territory. That is what I would like to take up here.

Although the Spirit Self will only come to full expression later in human evolution, we are beginning the work now. A key question is, has the Ego begun to spiritualise its own astrality? Steiner talks about the astral body becoming two-fold, part transformed, part untransformed. This transformation is an inner activity and cannot be seen outwardly. Yet the emerging Spirit Self is always working on the astral to change it, to develop it beyond its existing astrality. If this is the case, there may be two sets of questions for teacher educators:

- Do we understand and can we practice Steiner education, and
- What is active in us when we stand in front of our students, or any other adults?

This second question is far more exacting.

If we aim to encourage and support the emergence of Spirit Self in student teachers, then the environment around them must allow this. They need to be near someone who is actively working on themselves, someone for whom the struggle with the untransformed astral body is real, conscious and ongoing. They need to *experience* what it is like to be around a human being who is trying to grow in this direction.

At the same time, Steiner's description of how the pedagogical law operates reminds us that a teacher's influence works both positively and negatively. I believe we all know of examples within anthroposophical contexts of individuals who strive sincerely but may not always remain in full control of their astrality, leading to jealousy, having favourites, resentment, irritation, or the tendency to gossip, or act and speak out of their often-changing emotions. These things have a generally negative effect. Steiner's prerequisites for esoteric training (GA 10) make it clear that work on these aspects of the soul should begin early in one's inner practice. And yet, we see how hard this is to achieve.

On top of the other tasks the teacher educator must manage – delivering content, organising activities, working with difficult concepts and so on – Steiner's remark from the *Curative Course* remains central: "You have no idea how unimportant what the teacher says or does not say is on the surface, and how important the teacher's own being is." I believe this applies no less to those who teach adults as it does to those who work in early childhood. The developmental picture is different, but the principle is the same.

I am not writing here as someone who has the answers but rather someone for whom these are real questions. How do we work with this as Steiner teacher educators? Do we see it as important in our work? How much consideration do we give it? How do we remain forever on a path of development and not become content to remain where we are, showing students that the path of the Steiner teacher is one of constant self-transformation. Self-education.

Bibliography

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